

Use case fact-sheet

Actors

List all actors involved in the Use Case and the Geographic Information-related processes they are involved in, then put a “x” in correspondence to the relevant cells.

Who (actor) ²	What (Action) ¹				
	Data acquisition/creation	Data analysis/processing/validation	Data publication	Extraction of information from published data	Data maintenance
Municipality		x	x		
Decision makers				x	
Officers/technicians	x	x		x	
Researchers		x		x	
General Public	x	x	x		x
xxx					

Table 1: Overview of the actors involved in the Use Case

Use Case (UC) main info	
Identifier	FE_CS_BD
Name	Biodiversity, Roadkill and Pollinators
Description	Geolocation and mapping of all the kill roads. Mapping of all species of animals/insects (local and alien) with a special care for pollinators. Identification and characterization of the richest areas in biodiversity or most affected by certain species.
Primary User	Volunteer citizen scientists from local groups and associations, high schools students
Goal	Mapping of the most dangerous road stretches for vertebrates/drivers to adopt strategies to try to reduce the risks of accidents; to define important areas as reservoirs of pollinators, to protect and improve them. In general the goal is to monitor the trend of biodiversity and evaluate possible protection interventions at the level of planning and protection of the territory. For example, it should be important to define reduced mowing areas, design road crossing tunnels.

¹ Add new processes or rename the existing ones or split the ones currently merged as you may find more appropriate

² Add new actors or rename the existing ones

Owner	DEDA - MOF Natural History Museum (Carla Corazza)
Status	<i>In progress</i>
Policy context	
Challenges & Priorities	<i>Climate change has an impact on biological cycles which are subject to mismatching, such as early blooming of plants while pollinator insects are not yet active. Other challenges impacting biodiversity include land consumption, the destruction of natural habitats, the use of pesticides and herbicides in addition to glyphosate, and the overuse of mowing that risks removing the flowers that pollinator species feed on in addition to potentially destroying the natural habitats of some species. To these problems can be added the invasion by alien species, both plants and animals, which can alter the habitat and replace native species as well as contribute to the spread of pathogens.</i>
Strategy/Plan/Regulation	<p>Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP) is the main local policy instrument for deploying both mitigation and adaptation measures, containing risk and vulnerability assessments of the territory and identified intervention areas. The designed use case can make a tangible contribution to the following line of action:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● AD-B2: Ecological networks (action for adaptation) <p><i>This action aims to contribute to existing ecological networks through permanent monitoring instruments of the species, flora and fauna using indicators on the state of conservation of the ecosystem. The use case can concretely contribute to the setup and maintenance of this system while actively involving the community.</i></p>
Local Green Deal / City contract(s)	<p><i>The General Urban Plan (Piano Urbanistico Generale - PUG) is the general urban plan and planning tool that the General Planning and Landscape Office of the Municipality prepares, with reference to its entire territory, to outline the structural constraints and the strategic choices of urban planning and development within its competence, oriented mainly to the regeneration of the urbanised territory, the reduction of soil consumption and the environmental and territorial sustainability of uses and transformations.</i></p> <p><i>The Plan sets out a broad approach to the challenge connected to biodiversity in the Strategic Objective 1 addresses generally the urban capacity to adapt to climate change. To this end, the creation of a network of green and blue infrastructure is promoted to counter the conditions of fragility while maximising biodiversity and the production of ecosystem services. Project actions regarding land transformation have also a direct impact on biodiversity.</i></p>

<p>European Green Deal Policy Area</p>	<p><i>The European Green Deal identifies ecosystems as essential services for clean air, food and fresh water and the necessity to halt biological diversity loss as one key priority area of its measures. To this end, multiple interconnected strategies have been promoted in the last years, including the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the New Deal for Pollinators. This use case among other actions to support biodiversity will contribute to improving the knowledge about pollinators (database, decline, habitat); cataloguing species and habitats towards nature restoration targets; mobilising the society and relevant actors to participate in monitoring and conservation activities.</i></p>
<p>Precondition</p>	
<p>Actors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Groups of volunteers and high schools students (see https://citizenscienceferrara.org/). <p>Data requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - data on roadkill and pollinators presence with taxonomy, location and time of the observations - localization/distribution of tree species (both in public and private areas) points and canopy polygons - vegetation indexes (e.g. NDVI and others) - gardens/parks, land cover and materials (from hyperspectral images) - biotopes - characteristics of the roads <p>Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - iNaturalist app (https://www.inaturalist.org/) and web portal (with user guidelines) 	
<p>Postcondition</p>	
<p>DRI (Decision Ready Information)</p>	<p>Spatial data and statistics about biodiversity, road-kills and pollinators, based on standard specifications (national/EU) available and shareable with open licenses.</p> <p>Roadkill distribution surveyed with Inaturalist: https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/0f9c9ad5-e3e8-4fb2-88e9-422908c2c9e2</p> <p>Distribution of species surveyed with iNaturalist: https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/ce df359a-8389-4835-8b45-c9ab1720bffd</p> <p>Distribution of pollinators surveyed with inaturalist: https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/179894de-144d-4c0c-9a87-52f2431d5d95</p>

Use of DRI	The DRI will be used to monitor the trend of biodiversity over the years in the area of the municipality and Ferrara province with particular attention to pollinators and the issue of roadkills in order to evaluate possible interventions to protect flora and fauna
Use case processing steps	
FE-BD_BPMN.drawio	
DOI to processing steps BPMN	
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15350884	
Additional remarks	